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Conference Abstract

MAULANA MAUDUDI'S VIEW ON THE CORE ELEMENTS OF THE ISLAMIC SYSTEM: THE ROLE OF QURAN AND SEERAH IN SHAPING ITS FIVE KEY ASPECTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines Maulana Abdul A'la Maududi's perspective on the core elements of the Islamic System, with a focus on the crucial roles that the Quran and the Seerah (the life of Prophet Muhammad PBUH) play in shaping the system's five key aspects. Maulana Maududi, a distinguished Islamic scholar and thinker, presented a holistic framework that views Islam not only as a religion but as a comprehensive way of life. According to Maududi, the Quran serves as the divine guide, and the Seerah acts as the ideal model of the Prophet's (SAW) life, both offering the foundational principles needed to establish just, moral, and harmonious society. The five key aspects discussed in this framework include belief and worship (spiritual life), social justice, economic principles, governance, and law. Maulana Maududi emphasized that these elements are interconnected and must work together in the implementation of an Islamic System. The Quran provides clear guidance for maintaining justice, economic fairness, social equity, and personal piety, while the Seerah exemplifies how these principles were practically applied through the Prophet's (SAW) leadership and actions. This study highlights Maulana Maududi's vision of an Islamic society based on the Quranic and prophetic model, where these five aspects are harmoniously nurtured by divine teachings and practical leadership, offering insights into how his framework can be relevant and applied to modern socio-political systems.

Keywords: *Quran, Hadith, Seerah, Islamic books*

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